

Bakanae and foot rot disease incidence in Basmati 385 nursery in Punjab, Pakistan

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Bakanae and foot rot disease has become a serious disease of Basmati varieties, particularly Basmati 385, in Punjab, Pakistan. The disease can attack the rice plant from preemergence to flowering.

Disease incidence data have been recorded only from the transplanted crop in Pakistan. We conducted a survey to determine the bakanae and foot rot disease incidence in nurseries in traditional rice-growing areas of Sheikhpura, Gujranwala, and Sialkot districts during 1992.

Disease symptoms observed in the nurseries were discolored (whitish) seedlings, which were prevalent in nurseries up to 15-18 d after seeding, and elongated (thin and pale) seedlings, which were found at later stages. The data were recorded in a nursery from four randomly selected spots of 0.09 m² each. Seed source, seed treatment, and water source were also recorded.

Bakanae and foot rot disease incidence on Basmati 385 in the traditional rice-growing areas of Punjab, India. 1992.

Item	Sheikhpura	Gujranwala	Sialkot	Total
Nurseries checked (no.)	89	36	55	180
Diseased nurseries (%)	92.0	97.2	98.1	93.9
Treated seed nursery (%)	3.4	5.5	9.1	5.5
Untreated seed nursery (%)	96.6	94.5	90.9	94.5
<i>Seed source (%)</i>				
Farmers' own	89.8	86.1	94.5	90.5
Punjab Seed Corporation	5.6	-	1.9	3.3
Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku	2.2	2.8	1.9	2.2
Others	2.2	11.1	1.9	3.9
<i>Disease incidence (%)</i>				
Untreated seed				
0-12 d	10.5	6.5	5.6	-
13-24 d	5.4	3.6	3.8	-
25 d and more	1.2	1.7	2.5	-
Av	7.2	3.6	4.5	-
Treated seed	3.3	2.4	2.7	-
Reduction in disease incidence (%)	54.9	33.5	40.7	-

Seeds of 94.5% of the 180 nurseries surveyed were not treated with fungicide. Farmers used their own seed, produced from the previous year's crop, in most (90.5%) of the nurseries (see table). The high number of diseased nurseries (93.9%) might be due to infected seed, indicating the disease's seedborne nature.

Disease incidence was greater in younger nurseries and decreased with age. The highest average incidence (7.2%) was observed in Sheikhpura. Treating seed with a fungicide reduced the incidence 33.5-54.9%. ■

Using gypsum to manage sheath rot in rice

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Foliar application of salts (calcium sulfate, magnesium sulfate, and ammonium molybdate) reduced sheath rot (ShR) incidence, caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Grams and Hawksw, in an earlier greenhouse experiment. We conducted field trials to compare these treatments with soil application of calcium sulfate as gypsum during 1991-92 wet season (WS) (Sep-Feb) in two locations using variety Co 43. Plot size was 5 x 4 m²; treatments were laid out in a randomized block design. Gypsum, at 500 kg/ha, was applied basally and as a topdressing, singly and in combination. Salts and a fungicide, carbendazim, were

Effect of various salts on rice ShR incidence and grain yield.^a Aduthurai, India, 1991-92 WS.

Treatment	Time of application	Mean ShR incidence (%)		Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	50% basal + 50% at 35 d after transplanting (DAT)	21.8 ab	22.8 a	3.6 a	4.0 a
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	50% at 20 DAT + 50% at 35 DAT	20.1 a	21.9 a	3.6 ab	3.6 ab
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	Basal only	-	27.7 ab	-	3.4 ab
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	Topdress only at 25 DAT	-	30.6 b	-	3.7 c
Calcium sulfate 0.2%	Booting and 10 d later	26.5 abc	-	3.2 bcd	-
Magnesium sulfate 0.2%	Booting and 10 d later	28.1 bc	-	3.3 bcd	-
Ammonium molybdate 0.005%	Booting and 10 d later	26.3 abc	-	3.4 abc	-
Carbendazim 0.1%	Booting and 10 d later	20.7 ab	23.0 ab	3.4 ab	3.9 a
Untreated check		31.2 c	40.9 c	3.1 d	2.6 d

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.